

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B098
Date: 26 May 2005
Take Off: 09:44:18
Landing: 13:29:58
Flight Time: 3h 45m 40

Campaign: CWVS / CIRRUS
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: Chilbolton

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Charlie Whitaker	BAES
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Richard Cotton	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	CCN/CVI	Paul James	FAAM
7	Core Chemistry	Alan Woolley	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
9	CPI	Keith Bower	Manchester
10	AMS	Jonny Crosier	Manchester
11	Observer	Steve Ball	FAAM
12			
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Flight Track:

B098 Track 26-MAY-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B098
 Date: 26 May 2005
 Project: CWVS / Cirrus
 Location: Chilbolton

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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092851		INU to NAV Cranfield	0.30 kft	125 52	04.36N 000 37.48W
094418		T/O Cranfield	2.4 kft	316	09:44:18
094932		ASPs open	5.0 kft	263	
095328		video tapes	5.0 kft	225	FFC & DFC to record
100759	102232	Profile 1	3.6 - 18.0 kft	256	3500' to fl240 interrupted at fl180
102721	103514	Profile 1.2	18.0 - 25.0 kft	083	recommended interrupted at fl250
104107	104538	Profile 1.3	25.0 - 28.0 kft	250	recommended to fl280
105255	105943	Run 1	22.1 - 22.0 kft	086	fl220
110237	110832	Run 2	21.0 - 21.1 kft	251	fl210
111258	111853	Run 2.2	21.0 kft	087	towards Chilbolton overhead
112620	113258	Run 3	23.0 kft	252	fl230
113650	114055	Run 4	25.0 kft	079	fl250
114355	114906	Run 4.2	25.1 - 25.0 kft	255	fl 250 outbound
114921		Nev calcs	25.0 kft	258	
115345	115717	Run 5	27.0 kft	071	fl270
120028	121207	Run 5.2	27.1 - 27.0 kft	255	
121529	122232	Profile 2	27.1 - 32.0 kft	075	
122626	122908	Profile 2.2	32.1 - 33.1 kft	245	
123909	124520	Run 6	20.1 - 20.0 kft	088	fl200
125034	125607	Run 7	16.1 kft	250	fl160
130001	130406	Run 7.2	16.1 kft	080	
130450		end of science	15.0 kft	076	
130754		asp closed	7.0 kft	357	
132958		land Cranfield	0.28 kft	355	13:29:58
133448		Cranfield apron2	0.28 kft	307 52	04.36N 000 37.48W

B098 Track 26-MAY-05

4°W 3°W 2°W 1°W 0°

Top 10.5
 SLW 4 → 5 (-10 to -18°C) 253 rel.
 FL 3.0

Sortie Brief: CWVC – mixed-phase cloud studies

Flight Number: B098

Date: 26 May 2005

Sortie Aims: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes and cloud dynamics in stratiform cloud systems in association with Chilbolton radar.

Sortie Location: Within a stratiform cloud system over or to the west of Chilbolton radar facility.

Sortie Summary: Perform a series of runs along the azimuth that is being scanned by the radar. Information on the run orientation and altitude to be flown will be provided by scientists at Chilbolton using VHF radio (127.050 MHz, call-sign “Radsearch”). Where the radar identifies a small-scale feature of interest, the aircraft may abort a long leg in order to turn to re-penetrate it. In this case, the aircraft may fly a small butterfly pattern in which only one of the legs is parallel to the wind direction or radar azimuth. Where either the aircraft or radar identifies a particular horizontal layer of interest, the aircraft may fly a sawtooth pattern so as to provide a sequence of profiles. On occasion, the aircraft flight legs may start/finish in the Chilbolton overhead. This benefits the validation of vertically-pointing radar/lidar retrievals of supercooled cloud layers. This requires turns to be done within controlled airspace.

Sortie Detail:

- a) T+0 Take off and climb to FL090 for transit to the operating area west of Chilbolton. 3500m.n.
- b) T+40 When in a suitable location, perform a profile descent at 1000ft/min from FL200 to 1000ft agl or 1000 ft below the freezing level, whichever is the lower (20 min) PROFILE ASCENT 035 UP TO TOPS.
- c) T+60 Establish start/end points of 40-80km flight leg along the azimuth which is being scanned by the radar. Fly this leg at altitudes defined by the radar. Duration of each leg ~ 5-10 minutes. Some legs may be extended into the overhead position of Chilbolton when requested from the ground.
- d) Where the radar identifies a feature of interest that is penetrated by the aircraft along any leg, the leg may be interrupted to fly one or more butterfly patterns. Each butterfly consists of a minimum of two minutes straight/level that includes penetration of the feature followed by turns that allow re-penetration of the feature during the reciprocal part of the pattern (see diagram)

- e) Where a defined layer of interest (such as a shallow layer of supercooled liquid water) is identified by the aircraft or radar, the long leg may be flown as a sawtooth leg with ascents/descents at 1000ft/min, extending 1000ft above and below the layer level and with level segments of 1 minute.
- f) Items c) to e) may be repeated as long as flight endurance or cloud conditions permit.

PROJECT BRIEF: CWVC – mixed-phase cloud studies

Scientific Aims: The purpose of this project is to obtain detailed microphysical measurements in stratiform cloud systems that lie within the temperature regime in which mixed-phase clouds are possible (typically 0 to -30C). In particular, we wish to examine the competing roles of

- primary ice nucleation
- secondary nucleation via the Hallett-Mossop process, in which new ice particles are generated during the riming growth of larger ice particles.
- other secondary ice nucleation mechanisms such as evaporative break-up
- the dependence of these processes on the dynamical environment within the cloud (and in particular the strength of embedded convective updraughts)

In-situ measurements from the aircraft are performed in close coordination with the Camra radar facility at Chilbolton, Hants. The radar may identify features such as embedded convective cells or layers of supercooled liquid water that can be investigated more intensively by the aircraft. Similarly, the aircraft can provide information on microphysical characteristics to aid interpretation of the radar data.

Weather conditions: A stratiform cloud band lying over or to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. This may or may not be generating precipitation at the surface. It is particularly desirable if the mean wind direction lies between about 220 and 280 degrees. This allows the aircraft to fly legs along the radar beam whilst staying closely parallel to the mean wind direction, and hence to more easily penetrate identifiable cloud features on successive runs at the same altitude. Note that to avoid interference with Bournemouth airport, Chilbolton is NOT allowed to transmit in the sector 209 to 219 degrees true.

Key instruments and their operation.

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- GPS, INU, turbulence probe – When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud Physics

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, SID-1 (and SID-2). Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops (>100micron) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- ADA/CPI – as above
- CCN measurements should be made by filling the alleviator whilst in clear air either below, between or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest.
- If required, Ice Nucleus counter (INC) will normally be operated in clear air and under fixed conditions of temperature and supersaturation so as to maintain it in a stable condition. Allow additional time between runs for the operator to adjust it to a different set of conditions.
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where a run is only partially in cloud and is starting in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Manager's log.
- TWC. If possible, a profile in clear air is desirable for calibration purposes.

SORTIE DEBRIEF

CWVC Mixed Phase Cloud.

Flight number B098

26 May 2005

Assessment of the flight

Takeoff from Cranfield. Transit to operating area at FL050.

Profile (P1) starting above Chilbolton, from FL035 to FL270.

Run (R1) at FL220 inbound to Chilbolton. Radar reports problems, so do a stack of runs at various heights.

Run (R2) at FL210 outbound. In cloud, 4/8 Sc below.

Run (R3) at FL210 inbound.

Run (R4) at FL230 outbound, in cloud initially, but near base. Run out of cloud midway through run. For future runs, decrease time and do inbound and outbound at each height.

Run (R4.1) at FL250 inbound, in cloud initially. Run (R4.2) at FL250 outbound.

Run (R5.1) at FL270 inbound, in clear air or very patchy cloud. Run (R5.2) at FL270 outbound.

Profile (P2) from FL230 to FL310. Cannot reach cloud.

Run (R6) at FL200 inbound.

Transit back to Cranfield..

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci - Richard Cotton.

CWVC 2.2

Flight No **B.096**.....

Date **26/05/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	T to Chl	5000'	163	51.7N/1.6W	CPI / ADA not seeing anything
10:07:36	P1 st	3500'			Inclined Profile 3500-24000
10:18:50		14200			-4.79 / -10.25°C 590mb
10:21:40		17000			-11.4 / -14.71 25ms/22
10:22:31	P2 mt	FL180	248		
	P1 rec	FL180			-13.3 / -16.29 28ms/226
					Radar seeing cloud 20000-36000'
10:28:08					Inboard 100km Range
					CPI seeing crystals -
10:33:36	P1 st	23600	77	51.0/1.6W	-22.8 / -24.86°C 23/235° 393
10:35:13	P1 mt	25000			Combinations: P1, Binned R., poly X, S10, Drops?
10:38:00	P1 mt.	25000	251	51.0/1.6W	-26.05 / -27.24 375mb 26/233°
10:41:07	P1 rec.	FL250	251		→ FL280
10:41:08					
10:45:38	P1.3rd	FL280			End profile
10:46:40					Run 3 ADA (forget to start it) - sunlight only laser ~ 310
10:47:00					PCASP low 30/cm ³ measured Rad 0.2
10:48:19					AMS Wulms - turning TOF off CPC ~ 300
					ADA - No signal on Shilled - 120 on VSh
10:52:56	R1 st	FL220	79	50.9/2.6W	-19.4 / -19.11°C 20ms/231° 427mb
					800m
					vSIR + feathers Poly Xinds - 2D too
10:59:43	R1 end	FL22			End m
					Radar has Problem - can't see out for - go out to 60k

Mission Scientist's Log

M Sci - Richard Cotton.

CWVC 2.2

Flight No **B.098**.....

Date 26/05/05.....

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	GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
Out	11:02:36	R2 _{st}	FL 210	250	51.0N/1.6W	24/234° -16.85 / 17.53°C 44Smb (226 465)
	11:06:52	R2 _{end}	FL 210	"	50.9/2.2W	-17.58/-17.08 44Smb 10mb/233° (^{block} 194 / ^{unch} 276 ^{block} 230 / ^{ch} 230 - No Shells)
in.	11:12:58	R2.1 _s	FL 210	80	51.0/2.1W	To go ahead ChB. -17.69/-17.04 21/239 465
	11:18:55	R2.1 _e	FL 210	"	51.1/1.4W	Overhead ChB - end -16.50/-17.79 28/246 CEN Spectra Completed.
Out	11:26:19	R3	FL 230	252	51.0/1.6W	-21.66/-20.5°C 23/233 400mb CPI
	11:30:38					Come out of dead layer
	11:32:58	R3 _{end}	FL 230			End of Run - do re-orientation at FL 250
in.	11:36:49	R4 _{st}	FL 250	79	50.9/2.3W	-25.9/-24.98 375mb 21/244° 344mb
	11:40:58	R4 _{end}	FL 250		51.0/1.6W	
Out	11:43:54	R4.2 _{st}	FL 250	255	51.0/1.6W	375 -25.9/-24.83 25/235
	11:48:59	R4.2 _{en}	FL 250		50.9/2.2W	-27.5/-25.5°C 33/235
in.	11:53:46	R5	FL 270	72	50.9/2.2W	-30.77/-28.83 26/245 344mb (324mb)
	11:57:18	R5 _{en}			51.0/1.7W	343mb etc
Out	12:00:27	R5.2 _{st}	FL 270		51.0/1.6W	343 28/233 -30.87 / -29.55°C
	12:12:08	R5.2 _{en}	FL 270	269	50.5/2.9W	344. -30.42/-29.03°C 24/249.
in.	12:15:29	P2	FL 270		50.5/2.8W	P2. start - towards ChB - Clear Air Cloud to South - can't go there
	12:22:32	P2.1	FL 320		51.0/1.6W	end Probe - Diving
Out	12:26:26	P2.2 _{st}	FL 320	246	51.0/1.7	-43.6/-42.55 32/241 272mb
Out	12:29:08	P2.2 _{en}	FL 330			end - descending to bottom C _i Descent to ground for C _{pi} - Error Will Stop / Start Probe

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	Y
All cylinders pressures are OK	Y
Ozone Span = 504, Offset = 50	Y

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT	52	128	135
POST FLIGHT	30	125	135

POST POWER UP – GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
.4	.4	1.108	.065	.437
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	
Spot on!	33.95	1.09	7.13	

ZEROS							Average
Ozone (ppbV)	-1	1	0	-2	-2	-1	-0.8
NO (ppbV)	13.8	13.7	13.8	13.8	13.8	13.7	13.8
NO₂ (ppbV)	14.0	14.0	13.6	13.2	12.9	12.7	13.4
NO_x (ppbV)	27.7	27.4	27.4	26.7	26.7	26.4	27.1
SO₂ (ppbV)	-.71	-.21	-.42	-.54	-.09	-.52	-.42

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS

Apparent NO_x leak. Zeros rubbish and leak test flow does not approach zero.

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL		Date and Flight Level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
10:00 ish Bad cal	50	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		19.67	335.95	6608.59	50	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
33.87	.5	.5	1.100	.0063	.4		
10:11:08 Bad cal	35	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		75.05	85.45	6638.57	50	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
33.88	0.6	0.7	1.101	0.067	.366		
11:03:48	220	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		80.43	81.27	6536.16	50	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
33.48	.8	.8	1.023	.066	.220		
11:17:24	210	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		81.81	80.26	6565.67	50	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
33.93	.8	.8	1.022	0.066	0.216		
11:29:43	230	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		82.16	80.15	6584.82	50	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
33.89	0.8	0.8	0.067	1.017	0.198		
11:40:02	250	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		82.09	79.50	6526.3	50	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
33.93	.8	.8	1.002	.068	.170		
11:55:46	270	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		81.46	80.01	6517.8	50	7	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
33.94	.8	.8	1.012	.066	.151		

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
12:25:48	320	78.61	82.11	6454.25	50	6.27	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.82	.8	.8	.947	.062	0
Time	Flight Level	CO					
12:37:40	200	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		79.87	80.67	6443.63	50	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample		
		33.82	0.8	.8	1.019	0.066	.231
Time	Flight Level	CO					
12:53:36	160	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		80.55	81.02	6526.37	50	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample		
		33.88	.8	.8	1.051	.066	.278
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
Flows (LPM unless stated)							
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample		
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
Flows (LPM unless stated)							
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample		
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
Flows (LPM unless stated)							
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample		
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
Flows (LPM unless stated)							
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample		

FLIGHT NUMBER: B098	DATE: 26/05/05	OPERATOR: Alan Woolley	Page 4 of 4
PROJECT: CWVC, then CIRRUS when Chilbolton Radar broke...			

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

GENERAL COMMENTS

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B098

Date: 26/05/05

Operator: JT

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:07:58	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Profile 1 @ 3500ft
10:08:37	0	0	10	1000	0	0	0	0	0	0	4000ft
10:09:33	14	0.07	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	5000ft
10:10:34	12	0.07	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
10:11:31	2	0.07	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
10:12:24	32	0.08	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
10:13:27	27	0.08	11	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
10:14:29	28	0.08	11	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
10:15:27	37	0.08	11	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
10:16:29	20	0.08	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	12
10:17:24	15	0.08	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13
10:18:30	13	0.09	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14
10:19:27	28	0.09	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	15
10:20:27	17	0.09	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	16
10:21:27	21	0.09	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17
10:22:30	16	0.09	11	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	18 profile interputed
10:27:21	30	0.09	12	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	18 profile restarted
10:28:33	13	0.08	12	70	1	400	10	83	400	10	19
10:29:30	8	0.19	12	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	20
10:30:42	3	0.1	12	0	14	625	10	700	200	10	21
10:31:49	0	0.05	12	10	0.5	100	10	100	200	10	22
10:32:56	0	0.08	12	5	4.5	100	8	2800	200	8	23
10:34:08	0	0	12	0	3.5	200	8	33	200	8	24
10:35:13	2	0.1	13	100	15	450	8	3733	200	8	25 profile interrupted temp -26 dp
10:41:27	11	0.18	21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25 profile restarted
10:42:33	7	0.15	21	10	6	475	8	Noise			26
10:44:18	7	0.7	22	2	0	0	0	Noise	0	0	27
10:45:35	2	1.1 ??	23	100	11	250	10	Noise			28 profile stop
10:52:56	2	0.5	27	75	15	400	8	1725	400	8	Run 1 @ FL220
10:54:00	1	0.06	27	0	0.5	200	10	83	200	10	
10:56:00	6	0.1	27	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:58:10	7	0.7	27	80	25	525	8	2700	200	8	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B098

Date: 26/05/05

Operator: JT

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:59:45	8	0.06	28	10	17	500	9	1000	500	9	End or run 1
11:02:36	15	0.07	29	2	0	0	0	2000	200	8	Start run 2 @ FL210
11:04:00	21	0.15	29	10	6	650	8	975	800	8	
11:06:00	13	0.1	30	2	2	800	8	333	800	8	
11:08:30	7	0.14	30	70	4	500	8	1933	100	8	End of run 2
11:12:58	11	0.45	35	100	30	700	8	2983	100	8	Start run 2.1
11:14:00	20	0.15	35	10	3	600	8	283	1000	8	
11:16:00	19	0.07	36	10	7	600	8	3250	1500	8	
11:18:53	36	0.6	38	100	53	525	8	2883	800	8	End of run 2.1
11:26:20	1	0.1	42	100	44	375	8	4458	100	8	Start run 3 FL230
11:28:00	16	0.7	44	200	50	700	8	10650	800	8	
11:30:00	205	1.1	47	60	0.5	200	8	2750	500	8	
11:32:32	12	0.06	47	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 3
11:36:50	9	0.31	47	10	0.5	375	8	150	400	8	Start run 4 @ FL250
11:38:00	4	0.07	47	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:40:55	82	1.06	48	100	36	625	8	10983	800	8	End of Run 4
11:43:55	24	0.8	55	100	46	800	8	12691	800	8	Start of run 4.1
11:45:00	37	0.85	58	150	22	600	9	1150	600	9	
11:47:00	250	0.93	59	100	150	425	8	900	400	8	
11:49:46	7	0.29	60	100	18	200	10	700	400	10	End of run 4.1
11:53:45	2	0.05	60	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start Run 5 @ FL270
11:55:00	1	0.05	60	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:57:16	4	0.05	60	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of Run 5
12:00:27	1	0	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start of Run 5.1
12:02:00	1	0.05	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:04:00	1	0.06	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:06:00	12	0.16	61	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:08:00	16	0.07	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:10:00	4	0.08	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:12:07	11	0.1	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End Run 5.1
12:15:29	10	0.07	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start Profile @ FL270
12:16:42	3	0.07	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL280

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B

Date:

Operator:

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:17:51	4	0.08	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL290
12:19:00	2	0.08	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL300
12:20:29	2	0.08	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL310
12:22:32	5	0.06	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL320 End of Profile 2.1
12:26:26	1	0.11	61	0	0	0	0	37345 NOISE			FL320 recommence profile
12:29:08	4	0.09	61	2	0	0	0	NOISE			FL330 end of profile
12:39:09	7	0.08	61	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 6 @ FL200
12:41:00	7	0.07	61	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:43:00	14	0.07	61	0	0.5	100	1? sph	0	0	0	(spherical but -17C)
12:45:20	14	0.08	62	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	N.B. FFSSP 20 sec late
											End of run
											N.B. FFSSP 20 sec late
12:50:34	19	0.1	62	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 7 @ FL160
12:52:00	4	0.09	62	10	2.5	800	9	108	1000	9	
12:54:00	45	0.1	62	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:56:00	26	0.09	62	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 7
13:00:01	41	0.09	62	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start of run 7.1
13:02:00	42	0.08	62	7	1.5	800	8	280	800	8	
13:04:00	98	0.14	62	0	5	800	8	183	1000	8	End run 7

Flight No B098

CCNC LOG

Exp. Chilbortha.

Date 26/5/05

PAPS.

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ALLEVIATOR GMT		Height	TEMP INLET	STATIC						REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5		
111320	111400	210	25	0.49	0.72	1.08	1.41	2.05	S	
			24.49	486	651	875	642	754	D	
			24.49	389	388	385	386	393	B	
			26.07	2278	2287	2295	2300	2307	R	
				896.4	896.1	895.7	896.1	896.1	P	
<u>Run</u>			27.05	0.5	0.74	1.1	1.41	2.07	S	
4	113733	250	24.14	477	463	603	1227	1400	D	
	113815		22.7	417	412	410	424	463	B	
			22.64	2311	2324	2328	2327	2329	R	
			23.09	856	857	857	856	856.3	P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
1153	115345	270	23	0.50	0.72	1.1			S	
			23	349	409				D	<u>Failed</u>
				409	410	410			B	
				2304	2305	2300			R	
				836.8	836	837.7			P	
			22.65	0.5	0.73	1.09	1.42	2.07	S	
120110	1202	270	23.06	431	443	440	428	450	D	
				393	406	412	413	413	B	
				2286	2286	2285	2279	2279	R	
				836.4	836.8	836	837	837	P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
123930	124016	160	24	0.51	0.71	1.08	1.4	2.02	S	
			23.71	431	444	589	820	623	D	
			23.5	399	416	426	430	438	B	
			24.5	424	2279	2294	2296	2288	R	
			24.5	904	922	937	937.6	937	P	
125515	1256	160	24.75	0.5	0.72	1.1			S	
			24	484	497	648			D	
			24	412	454	468			B	
					2349	2356			R	
				2278	937.4	937.6			P	
				937.3						

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B098**

Date: 25/05/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	<u>Probes</u>		
GPS		Y	FFSSP	Y	Y
Satcom C		Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-P	Y	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	Y	Y
De-Iced Temp		Y	Cloudscope	N	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Heimann	N		SID 2	Y	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>					
G. Eastern		Y	HVPS	N	
J. Williams		Y	CIP25	Y	N
Nevzorov		Y	CIP100	Y	N
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	<u>Racks:</u>		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	N		<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	n
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
ECGC	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	n
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	Y
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	n
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS		n
PERCA	Y	N	Bag Sampling		n
WAS	Y	n			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B098

Date: 26/05/05

Instruments

1. Video – RFC display out of focus. Inboard display switches off .
2. otherwise ops normal:
 3. Cloud Physics
 4. core chem
 5. CCN

Aircraft

Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B098:

Log	Reason
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

Video recordings from this flight reside with FAAM (at 31 Oct 2005) :

- 2 x Forward Facing Cameras
- 2 x Downward Facing Cameras